

On Noncoherent FSK Reception with Doppler Frequency Uncertainty for Space Communications

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Abstract—This paper studies the mutual information for a general form of orthogonal M-ary frequency-shift keying modulations with non-coherent detection and Doppler frequency uncertainty at the receiver. The signal model includes as particular cases classical MFSK and special MFSK modulations, the later has been used in space communications for reporting spacecraft status and events during critical phases. The optimal code rates that minimize the energy-per-bit to noise power spectral density ratio required for reliable communications are studied. In addition, optimal and suboptimal metrics for soft-decoders are proposed for non-fading channels with or without average signal and noise power estimation and used to evaluate the performance of LDPC codes.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE choice of frequency-shift keying (FSK) modulation or, any other form of orthogonal signaling like pulse position modulation (PPM) with non-coherent detection is an attractive option when the phase of the received signal varies significantly from symbol to symbol and cannot be reliably estimated over time. This is typically the case when, in combination with very low receive signal power and/or severe channel distortion effects, there are either high Doppler dynamics due to a significant relative motion between transmitter and receiver, strong phase noise in local oscillators, or an unmitigated frequency offset in the down converted signal.

	DFU (Hz)	DFRU (Hz / s)	CNR (dBHz)
EDL	50000	700	14.2
S&S	100	1.5	6
Solar X/Ka-band	100/400	1.5/6	30

TABLE I: Scenarios and channel conditions parameters for typical TM/TC communications in deep space missions with high Doppler dynamics and/or low signal levels.

Examples of events in deep space where non-coherent reception for telemetry (TM) and telecommand (TC) is needed are summarized in Table I. There, we provide Doppler dynamics parameters, including Doppler frequency uncertainty

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This work has been supported by the European Space Agency under contract No. 4000135210/21/D/MB. The work of J. Gómez-Vilardebó, X. Mestre and Monica Navarro was supported in part under Grant 2021 SGR 00772 funded by the Universities and Research Department from Generalitat de Catalunya.

(DFU) and Doppler frequency rate uncertainty (DFRU), as well as the received carrier to noise ratio (CNR) levels at distances in the order of 2 Astronomical Units (AUs), i.e. Mars missions. In the Entry, Descent and Landing (EDL) situation [1], [2] the severe Doppler dynamics comes from the atmospheric environment. These Doppler dynamics can not be possibly compensated by the receiver from the information of the estimated spacecraft orbital data and the frequency plan of the spacecraft transmitter. In the Safe and Survival (S&S) event, the spacecraft is out of control or damaged and thus directional communication with high gain directional antennas is not possible. Then, the received signal level is as low as 6 dB-Hz making it challenging to compensate even moderate Doppler dynamics. Finally, the Solar Scintillation event occurs when the radio signal is traversing the solar corona, and the signal experiences deep fades caused by solar plasma. Doppler dynamics compensation is very hard during these fade events, despite the average received signal level may be high due to the possibility of using high gain directive antennas [3], [4]. In all these conditions, coherent detection is not possible and the spacecraft typically uses FSK tones for non-coherent detection.

A number of studies from, both, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the European Space Agency (ESA) have been conducted in the last 20 years supporting the use of orthogonal M-FSK signaling for communications in deep space missions. In particular, NASA has produced several studies mostly focusing on the EDL scenario for Juno Mission and Mars Science laboratory rover mission [1], [5]–[8]. Similarly, previous ESA studies on EDL communication technology for the Mars mission [2] identified M-FSK as the best waveform for direct transmission to Earth of very low bit rate telemetry in deep space. In addition, two other ESA studies have been recently conducted considering the use of M-FSK in combination with error-correcting codes for reliable TM and TC during superior solar conjunctions, when the signal either coming from the spacecraft (Telemetry-TM) or reaching it (Telecommand-TC), is crossing the solar plasma, see [9, RESCUE], [10, HELIOS], and related references [3], [4]. In these settings, M-FSK was demonstrated to provide reliable communication when coherent demodulation is not possible due to the scintillation effects in the receiver tracking loops. In addition, joint ESA/NASA works i.e. Ice Giants [11] have already identified the need to develop international standards covering M-FSK to enable and facilitate inter agency cross support.

Other examples outside deep space missions, where non-coherent receivers are currently considered include military

systems using fast frequency hopping communications, high velocity platforms such as missiles with very high Doppler dynamics events, as well as wireless sensor networks using cheap oscillators. Indeed, the IEEE 802.15.4 standard [12], used for the Internet of Things (IoT), contains several physical layers, which also employ non-orthogonal FSK modulation including smart utility networks (SUN), TV white space (TVWS), and rail communications and control land mobile radio (RCC LMR).

The study of the communication limits for the M -ary FSK modulation with non-coherent reception (unknown phase for the received signal) can be traced back to [13]–[15]. In particular, in [14] the capacity expression for memoryless Rician slow fading channels (channel attenuation is constant during every symbol duration, and independent from symbol to symbol) was derived. The evaluation of the capacity for a modulation size $M = 2$ in [13], [14] and $M = 4, 8, 16$ and 64 in [16] revealed a non trivial optimal code rate for energy efficient communications. In coherent communications, the minimum energy-per-bit to noise power spectral ratio, $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$, monotonically increases with the coding rate R , measured in information symbols/channel access, thus is minimized as $R \rightarrow 0$, whereas $R \rightarrow \infty$ requires $\frac{E_b}{N_0} \rightarrow \infty$. In contrast, in non-coherent channels, the required $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ is known to grow to infinity as either $R \rightarrow 0$ or $R \rightarrow 1$, and thus there exists a non-trivial optimal rate $R \neq 0$ for which the required $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ is minimized.

Achieving the mutual information data transmission rate for non-coherent channels requires maximum-likelihood (ML) decoding, which is hard to implement in practice since it involves highly nonlinear functions (the Bessel function and exponential functions). Thus, simplified symbol decoder metrics were proposed by approximating the ML transition probability function. In particular, [14] proposed the *square-law combining* metric, which is a linear function of the square of the matched filter output (the energy measured at the received tones), with a scale factor that depends on the average signal and noise power. This decoder metric is optimal for the Rayleigh fading channel with a fade level unknown at the receiver and was shown to provide excellent performance over additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) channels. For the case of an unknown instantaneous fading amplitude and average signal and noise powers, [16] proposed a parameter free version of the square-law combining metric.

Besides the *classical* MFSK modulation, i.e. one tone per symbol, which all mentioned above previous works on communication limits consider, in space communications, an alternative form of orthogonal MFSK modulation, here referred to as *special*, has been used for reporting spacecraft status and events during critical phases [5]–[8]. For the special MFSK, a symbol is represented by a carrier signal and subcarrier tones such that the symbol information is encoded in the frequency separation between the carrier signal and the subcarrier tones. These works propose symbol detectors that are robust to strong Doppler frequencies and Doppler frequency rate, based on a two phase detection, in which first the Doppler frequency is estimated and compensated only using the carrier signal

and then the symbol is detected only from the energy at the subcarriers tones.

In this work, first, motivated by the special MFSK modulation form, we consider a general form of orthogonal frequency modulation, in which a symbol is described by an arbitrary tone pattern, defined by a set of tone frequencies and tone coefficients. The model includes, as particular cases, the classical and the special MFSK modulation. For this modulation, we formulate the optimal non-coherent receiver, which in contrast to the two phase architecture proposed in previous works, is shown to require a joint estimation of the Doppler and the symbol information. When particularized to the special MFSK this implies joint symbol and Doppler detection from both carrier signal and subcarrier tones.

Finally, despite the relevance of the high Doppler dynamics scenario when motivating the use on non-coherent orthogonal communications, to the best of our knowledge, the impact of the DFU in the mutual information of non-coherent channels has not yet been studied in the literature. Moreover, most of the works considering the special MFSK modulation, have limited their discussion to uncoded transmission. We extend the analysis to coded transmission by evaluating the mutual information of this channel and discussing the impact of the DFU. In particular, we show that the relevant parameter in this case is the product between the DFU (which is measured in Hz) and the symbol duration T_s in seconds. Moreover, we derive optimal and suboptimal decoding metrics, with or without requiring signal and noise power estimation, and evaluate their performance for low density parity check (LDPC) codes under different code rates.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In Section II we describe the signal model. Section III, presents the optimal symbol detector and the more practical near-optimal symbol detector that results from the discretization of the Doppler frequency search space. We then derive the statistical distribution of the detector output under some additional mild assumptions. In Section IV we provide the mutual information expression for the ML detector and evaluate numerically the effect of the DFU as well as the receiver computational complexity. Finally, in Section V we derive the optimal and suboptimal but practical decoder metrics and evaluate their performance in terms of “mismatched” mutual information as well as in terms of codeword error rate when in combination with LDPC codes. Concluding remarks are given in Section VI.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

For the transmitted discrete time baseband signal model, we consider a generalization of the classical M -ary FSK signaling, where the symbol information is carried out by a tone pattern, rather than by the absolute position of a single symbol tone. The model also includes, as a particular case, the special MFSK modulated signals used in space communications [5]–[8], for which the tone pattern of a given symbol is defined by a sequence of tones separated by a constant frequency amount, which is different for each symbol, (see further details below). Specifically, let M be the modulation order, and let $\mathcal{F}_s = \{f_{1,s}, \dots, f_{L_s,s}\} \in [-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}]^{L_s}$

and $\mathcal{A}_s = \{\alpha_{1,s}, \dots, \alpha_{L_s,s}\} \in \mathbb{C}^{L_s}$ be, respectively, the set of discrete signaling frequency tones and tone complex coefficients that together define the tone pattern associated to information symbol $s \in \mathcal{M} = \{0, \dots, M-1\}$. We emphasize here that the number of signaling tones per symbol, L_s , may be infinite. We force the tone complex coefficients to satisfy $\sum_{l=1}^{L_s} |\alpha_{l,s}|^2 = 1$ for all s , so that, the transmitted signal for symbol s at sampling time index $n \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$ is given by

$$x_s[n] = \sqrt{P_T} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \alpha_{l,s} \exp j(2\pi f_{l,s}n + \theta) \quad (1)$$

where P_T is the transmitted power, and θ is a unknown phase. Notice that, in general, this simplified signal model does not guarantee constant amplitude signals, which are usually needed for energy efficient signal amplifiers. For a practical transmitted signal design one should also impose constraints on the peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR). For simplicity, here, we particularize our study to two constant amplitude signals, which we refer to as classical and special MFSK signals. For the classical MFSK, we particularize the above signal model by using only one tone per symbol, i.e. setting $\mathcal{F}_s = \{f_s\}$ and $\mathcal{A} = \{\alpha_{l,s} = 1\}$ for $s \in \{0, \dots, M-1\}$, then

$$x_s^{\text{MFSK}}[n] = \sqrt{P_T} \exp j(2\pi f_s n + \theta). \quad (2)$$

For the special MFSK, the transmitted signal for symbol s is given by

$$x_s^{\text{SMFSK}}[n] = \sqrt{P_T} \exp j(\Delta \text{sqr}(2\pi f_s n) + \theta) \quad (3)$$

where Δ is referred to as the *modulation index*, and where the function $\text{sqr}(x)$ can be either $\text{sqr}(x) = \sin(x)$, for a *sinusoidal* waveform or $\text{sqr}(x) = \text{sign}(\sin(x))$ for the *square*, also referred to as *hard-limited sine* waveform. By, expanding (3) in terms of its constituent tones, we can write (3) as

$$x_s^{\text{SMFSK}}[n] = \sqrt{P_T} \sum_{l=-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{\alpha}_l \exp j(2\pi l f_s n + \theta) \quad (4)$$

where the tone coefficients are in this case real valued and given by

$$\tilde{\alpha}_l = \begin{cases} J_l(\Delta) & l \geq 0 \\ (-1)^{-l} J_{-l}(\Delta) & l < 0 \end{cases}$$

for the sinusoidal waveform, and by

$$\tilde{\alpha}_l = \begin{cases} \cos \Delta & l = 0 \\ \frac{2}{\pi} \sin(\Delta) \delta_{l \text{ odd}} & l > 0 \\ (-1)^{-l} \frac{2}{\pi} \sin(\Delta) \delta_{-l \text{ odd}} & l < 0 \end{cases}$$

for the square wave form. Where δ_x is one if x is true and 0 otherwise. Notice that from (3), the special MFSK signal also has constant amplitude, as it is convenient for the efficiency of signal amplifiers, but at the cost of an infinite bandwidth. In the strict sense, this implies that the sampled representation in (1) does not hold exactly. However, in practice the magnitude of the coefficients $\tilde{\alpha}_l$ decay quickly with l , so that the representation in (1) is fairly accurate. In

the context of this work, we shall assume that the special MFSK signal is low pass filtered at reception before analog to digital conversion, and also possibly at transmission, and thus only a finite number of tones $L = L_s$ for all s , need to be considered. Accordingly, we also normalize the amplitude coefficients as needed, i.e. $\alpha_l = \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_l}{\sqrt{\sum_m |\tilde{\alpha}_m|^2}}$ for $l \in \{-\frac{L-1}{2}, \dots, \frac{L-1}{2}\}$. In that case, we can express (4) in terms of our signal model by defining for symbol s , the tone set $\mathcal{F}_s = \{0, \pm f_s, \pm 2f_s, \dots, \pm (\frac{L-1}{2}) f_s\}$, and the tone complex coefficient set $\mathcal{A}_s = \{\alpha_0, \alpha_{-1}, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{-\frac{L-1}{2}}, \alpha_{\frac{L-1}{2}}\}$. The latter being common to all symbols.

Next, going back to the general signal model, we express the N samples of the discrete time based band signal for symbol s in (1), in vector form as

$$\mathbf{x}_s = A \mathbf{g}_{N,s}$$

where $A = \sqrt{P_T} e^{j\theta}$ and with

$$\mathbf{g}_{N,s} = \sum_{j=1}^{T_i} \alpha_{j,s} \mathbf{d}_N(f_{j,s}) \quad (5)$$

and where we have defined

$$\mathbf{d}_N(f) = [1, \exp(j2\pi f), \dots, \exp(j2\pi(N-1)f)]^T.$$

Regarding the received signal, in addition to the AWGN, we model the effects of the Doppler frequency and the residual sampling time offset errors (assumed here to be a multiple of the sampling period). Let us denote by τ^0 the true discrete time symbol error and by f_D^0 the true discrete Doppler frequency. Omitting the signal contamination from adjacent symbols for simplicity, the output of the channel corresponding to the transmission of symbol s is then given by

$$y_s[n] = H \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \tilde{\alpha}_{l,s} \exp j(2\pi(f_{l,s} + f_D^0)n) + w_s[n]$$

where $w_s[n] \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ are zero-mean circularly symmetric complex independent Gaussian noise samples with variance σ^2 , and the received complex coefficient of tone l of symbol s is given by $H \tilde{\alpha}_{l,s}$, where $H = \sqrt{P_R} e^{j\theta'}$ and $\tilde{\alpha}_{l,s} = \alpha_{l,s} e^{-j2\pi(f_{l,s} - f_D^0)\tau^0}$ is the received complex coefficient for tone l of symbol s . In vector form, we can express the N samples at the output of the channel as

$$\mathbf{y}_s = H \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \tilde{\alpha}_{l,s} \mathbf{d}_N(f_{l,s} + f_D^0) + \mathbf{w}_s. \quad (6)$$

III. NON-COHERENT RECEIVER

Let the transmitted symbol be denoted by s^0 . The optimal (maximum-likelihood) non-coherent symbol detector consists of first applying to the received signal \mathbf{y}_{s^0} , the matched filter associated to each of the symbol candidates $s \in \{0, \dots, M-1\}$ and each possible Doppler frequency $f_D \in \mathcal{F}_D$, in order to maximize the energy captured from the received signal, and then select the output of maximum magnitude. For our signal model, the matched filter at the receiver is given by

$$\mathbf{h}^H|_{s,f_D} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \alpha_{l,s}^* e^{j2\pi(f_{l,s} - f_D^0)\tau^0} \mathbf{d}_N^H(f_{l,s} + f_D).$$

Observe that due to the residual sample time offset τ^0 , and possibly other channel effects that we are ignoring in this simplified channel model, obtaining the matched filter at receiver may require the estimation of the phase of each individual tone transmitted for a given symbol. Under this simplified model, this is something we could address by formulating a joint detection of the triplet $(\tau^0, f_D, f_{l,s})$. However, avoiding tone phase estimation is the main reason for adopting non-coherent detection and thus doing that would go against our purpose. Accordingly, we restrict the proposed non-coherent receiver to only apply a matched filter to every possible received tone, i.e.

$$\mathbf{h}^H|_{s,f} = \frac{\mathbf{d}_N^H(f)}{\sqrt{N}}$$

and take the absolute square of the resulting magnitude to remove the unknown phases of the received tones. Then, the signal we consider for detection is given by

$$r(f) = \left| \frac{\mathbf{d}_N^H(f)}{\sqrt{N}} \mathbf{y} \right|^2 \quad (7)$$

for all frequencies $f \in [0, 1)$. Let us denote by $\mathbf{r} = \{r(f) : f \in [0, 1)\}$. Then, the optimum (maximum-likelihood) reception consists in jointly searching for the Doppler frequency $f_D \in \mathcal{F}_D$ and the transmitted symbol $s \in \mathcal{M}$, by evaluating the channel transition probability $p(\mathbf{r}|_{s,f_D})$ of receiving \mathbf{r} conditioned to every possible transmitted symbol and Doppler frequency, and selecting the maximum, namely

$$[s, f_D] = \operatorname{argmax}_{s \in \mathcal{M}, f_D \in \mathcal{F}_D} p(\mathbf{r}|_{s,f_D}).$$

In practice, however, we need to discretize the search space. Thus, in the following we consider a suboptimal, but practical receiver, in which we discretize the search space into the N frequencies $f \in \{\frac{n}{N} : n = 0, \dots, N-1\}$. To simplify the notation, hereafter, we write $r[n]$ and $\mathbf{d}_N^H[n]$ instead of $r(\frac{n}{N})$ and $\mathbf{d}_N^H(\frac{n}{N})$, respectively, and also redefine \mathbf{r} as $\mathbf{r} = [r[0], \dots, r[N-1]]^T$. The statistical analysis of this magnitude is greatly simplified with this choice for the discretization of the search space, as then the set of vectors $\mathbf{d}_N^H[n]$ forms an orthogonal bank of filters for the received signal and the noise contribution at the output is statistically independent across the entries of \mathbf{r} . To further simplify the statistical analysis, we will assume that, both the signaling frequencies pattern $\mathcal{F}_s^0 = \{f_{1,s}^0, \dots, f_{L_s,s}^0\}$ of every symbol s , as well as the true Doppler frequency f_D^0 , are multiple of the inverse of the samples per symbol. In other words, we will assume that

$$f_{l,s^0} = \frac{m_{l,s^0}}{N}, f_D^0 = \frac{k_D^0}{N}$$

for integers m_{l,s^0}, k_D^0 . This is equivalent to a best case scenario for which the full received tone energies are captured, and thus the results here obtained shall be considered as upper-bounds on the performance of the near-optimal detector.

To obtain the channel transition probabilities $p(\mathbf{r}|_{s,f_D})$, we need to first characterize the statistical behavior of $r(\frac{n}{N})$.

that, substituting \mathbf{y} in (6) into $r(\frac{n}{N})$ in (7) for $n = 0, \dots, N-1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} r[n] &= \left| H \sum_{l=1}^{L_{s^0}} \tilde{\alpha}_{l,s^0} \frac{\mathbf{d}_N^H[n] \mathbf{d}_N[m_{l,s^0} + k_D^0]}{\sqrt{N}} + \frac{\mathbf{d}_N^H[n] \mathbf{w}}{\sqrt{N}} \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \left| \frac{\sqrt{2NH}}{\sigma} \sum_{l=1}^{L_{s^0}} \tilde{\alpha}_{l,s^0} \delta(n - (m_{l,s^0} + k_D^0)) + \frac{\mathbf{d}_N^H[n] \sqrt{2\mathbf{w}}}{\sqrt{N} \sigma} \right|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Next, from conventional statistics, we can readily see that the entries in $r[n]$ are distributed as independent non-central chi-square random variables with 2 degrees of freedom, that is

$$r[n] \sim \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \chi_2^2(\lambda(n, s^0, k_D^0))$$

where, noting that $|\alpha_{l,s}|^2 = |\tilde{\alpha}_{l,s}|^2$, the non-centrality parameter, λ , is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(n, s^0, k_D^0) &= \frac{2NH^2}{\sigma^2} \sum_{l=1}^{L_{s^0}} |\alpha_{l,s^0}|^2 \delta(n - (m_{l,s^0} + k_D^0)) \\ &= \sum_{l=1}^{L_{s^0}} \lambda_{l,s^0} \delta(n - (m_{l,s^0} + k_D^0)) \end{aligned}$$

with $\lambda_{l,s} = 2 \frac{E_s}{N_0} |\alpha_{l,s}|^2$ and where $E_s = |H|^2 T_s = \frac{|H|^2 N}{B_w}$ is the received signal energy for a symbol duration T_s , where $\sigma^2 = N_0 B_w$ is the noise power, N_0 is the noise power spectral density and B_w is the reception bandwidth.

Recall that the probability density function of the non-central Chi-square distribution, with 2 degrees and non-centrality parameter λ is given by

$$f_{2,\lambda}(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{-\frac{(x+\lambda)}{2}} I_0(\sqrt{\lambda x}) \quad (8)$$

where $I_0(x)$ is the zeroth order modified Bessel function of the first kind, which for $\lambda = 0$ (central Chi-square) particularizes to

$$f_{2,0}(x) = \frac{1}{2} e^{-\frac{x}{2}}. \quad (9)$$

Let $\mathcal{N}^0 = \{n^0 = m_{l,s^0} + k_D^0 : l = 1, \dots, L_{s^0}\}$ be the set of received tone indices for the true transmitted symbol s^0 and the true Doppler frequency $f_D^0 = \frac{k_D^0}{M}$, and let $\bar{\mathcal{N}}^0$ be the complementary set. Denote $\lambda_n^0 = \lambda_{j,s^0}$ for $n = m_{j,s^0} + k_D^0$ and $l = 1, \dots, L_{s^0}$, then the channel transition probability is given by

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{r}|_{s^0, k_D^0}) &= \prod_{n \in \mathcal{N}^0} f_{2,\lambda_n^0}(\bar{r}[n]) \prod_{n \in \bar{\mathcal{N}}^0} f_{2,0}(\bar{r}[n]) \\ &= \kappa \prod_{n \in \mathcal{N}^0} e^{-\frac{\lambda_n^0}{2}} I_0(\sqrt{\lambda_n^0 \bar{r}[n]}) \\ &= \kappa \prod_{l=1}^{L_{s^0}} e^{-\frac{\lambda_{l,s^0}}{2}} I_0\left(\sqrt{\lambda_{l,s^0} \bar{r}[m_{j,s^0} + k_D^0]}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where we have defined $\bar{r}[n] = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} r[n]$ and where $\kappa = 2^{-N} e^{-\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N r[n]}{\sigma^2}}$ is a constant for a given received signal \mathbf{r} .

Finally, we can derive the channel transition probability of receiving \mathbf{r} if the transmitted symbol is s^0 . For that, let us denote by \mathcal{K}_D the set of possible Doppler tones $\frac{k_D^0}{N}$ with $k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D$, and assume they are uniformly distributed, i.e. $p(k_D^0 = k_D) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}_D|}$ for all $k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D$ and $p(k_D^0 = k_D) = 0$ if $k_D \notin \mathcal{K}_D$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} p(\mathbf{r}|s^0) &= \sum_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} p(k_D^0 = k_D) p(\mathbf{r}|s^0, k_D) \\ &= \frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}_D|} \sum_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} p(\mathbf{r}|s^0, k_D) \\ &= \frac{\kappa}{|\mathcal{K}_D|} \Psi_s(\mathbf{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

with

$$\Psi_s(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \prod_{l=1}^{L_{s^0}} e^{-\frac{\lambda_{l,s}}{2}} I_0 \left(\sqrt{\lambda_{l,s^0} \bar{r}[m_{j,s} + k_D^0]} \right). \quad (12)$$

For the important particular case where tone coefficients are common to all symbols, which is the case for, both, special and classical MFSK, we can set $L = L_s$ and $\lambda_j = \lambda_{j,s}$ for all s . Then, noting that $\lambda = \sum_{j=1}^L \lambda_j = 2 \frac{E_s}{N_0}$, (11) simplifies to

$$p(\mathbf{r}|s^0) = \frac{\kappa'}{|\mathcal{K}_D|} \Psi_s(\mathbf{r})$$

with

$$\Psi_s(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \prod_{l=1}^L I_0 \left(\sqrt{\lambda_j \bar{r}[m_{l,s} + k_D^0]} \right) \quad (13)$$

and $\kappa' = 2^{-N} e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda}{2} + \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} r[n]}{\sigma^2}\right)}$ is constant.

For the special MFSK, in addition, the signaling frequencies associated to a symbol are multiples of the main signaling frequency, this is $m_{l,s} = l m_s$, so that (13) particularizes to

$$\Psi_s^{\text{SMFSK}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \prod_{l=-\frac{L-1}{2}}^{\frac{L-1}{2}} I_0 \left(\sqrt{\lambda_l \bar{r}[l m_s + k_D^0]} \right). \quad (14)$$

Finally, for the classical MFSK, there is only one tone per symbol and thus (13) simplifies to

$$\Psi_s^{\text{MFSK}}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} I_0 \left(\sqrt{\lambda \bar{r}[m_s + k_D^0]} \right). \quad (15)$$

IV. MUTUAL INFORMATION

Given the channel transition probability $p(\mathbf{r}|s)$, we can evaluate the mutual information in symbols per channel use of our non-coherent MFSK channel. For simplicity, we force a uniform probability distribution for the transmitted symbols. This is the capacity achieving distribution for the classical MFSK, but suboptimal in general [14]. In that case, we can lower bound the mutual information expression and thus, the capacity as follows. Let S represent the discrete random

variable associated to the input symbol and \mathbf{R} the multidimensional continuous variable associated to the channel output \mathbf{r} , then

$$\begin{aligned} I(S; \mathbf{R}) &\triangleq \int_{\mathbf{r}} \sum_{s^0=0}^{M-1} P\{S = s^0\} p(\mathbf{r}|S = s^0) \log_2 \frac{p(\mathbf{r}|S = s^0)}{p(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r} \\ &\geq \min_{s^0} \int_{\mathbf{r}} p(\mathbf{r}|S = s^0) \log_2 \frac{p(\mathbf{r}|S = s^0)}{p(\mathbf{r})} d\mathbf{r} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$= \log_2 M - \max_{s^0} \int_{\mathbf{r}} p(\mathbf{r}|X = s) \quad (17)$$

$$\log_2 \left(1 + \sum_{\forall s \neq s^0} \frac{p(\mathbf{r}|S = s)}{p(\mathbf{r}|S = s^0)} \right) d\mathbf{r} \quad (18)$$

$$= \log_2 M - \max_{s^0} \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{r}|s^0} \left[\log_2 \left(1 + \sum_{\forall s \neq s^0} \Delta_{s,s^0}(\mathbf{r}) \right) \right] \quad (19)$$

where we have imposed the uniform input distribution to obtain equality (18) and with $\Delta_{s,s^0}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{p(\mathbf{r}|S=s)}{p(\mathbf{r}|S=s^0)} = \frac{\Psi_s(\mathbf{r})}{\Psi_{s^0}(\mathbf{r})}$. For MFSK signals, thanks to the symmetry of the channel transition probability which implies the optimality of the uniform input distribution, we can remove the maximization over s^0 in (19) and the lower-bound is tight [14]. However this is not the case in general and specifically for special MFSK signals. In any case, the direct evaluation of the multi-dimensional integral in (19) requires a large amount of computations and is impractical for N values higher than 8. Instead, we can efficiently compute the mutual information formula (19) numerically via Monte Carlo's method, as suggested in [15], [17]. For that, we simply generate $\bar{r}[n]$ according to the Chi-squared distribution $\bar{r}[n] \sim \mathcal{X}_2^2(\lambda \delta_{n-n^0})$. Notice that the mutual information only depends on the $\frac{E_s}{N_0}$, through $\lambda = 2 \frac{E_s}{N_0}$.

A. The effect of Doppler frequency uncertainty

By evaluating the mutual information expression in (19), here we discuss the effect of the DFU in terms of the minimum energy per bit to noise power spectral density, $\frac{E_b}{N_0} = \frac{E_s}{N_0 \log_2(M)R}$, as a function of the code rate, R . Given a DFU, a tone at reception may have moved \pm DFU Hz from the nominal signaling frequency. We particularize the discussion to the classical and the special MFSK (with just three tones, i.e. $L = 3$) modulations, introduced in Section II. These two modulations are representative of two fundamentally different modulation design principles. For the classical MFSK, all the signal energy is concentrated in just one tone, and thus the difference between the signal and the noise level is maximized, which benefits the probability of symbol detection. However, if a symbol is represented by just one tone, then symbol frequencies need to be separated by at least 2DFU, increasing the sampling frequency and thus, the number of samples per symbol or, equivalently, the number of tentative tone locations, N , for a fixed symbol duration. This increases the probability of having a noise level higher than the signal level at an arbitrary tone location candidate and thus, decreases

the probability of symbol detection. Instead, for the special MFSK, the signal energy is spread across multiple signaling tones, which reduces the difference between the signal and the noise levels and thus decreases the probability of symbol detection. In contrast, as the symbol information is now carried by the separation between symbol tones, signaling tones from adjacent symbols can be as close as the receiver frequency resolution, decreasing the required sampling frequency, and thus, N , improving the probability of symbol detection.

For this comparison, let us fix the product $n_{DFU} = F_{DFU}T_s$, where T_s is the symbol duration in seconds and F_{DFU} denotes the DFU in Hz, and let $F_s = \frac{N}{T_s}$ denote the sampling frequency. For the MFSK modulation, as mentioned above, the signaling tones need to be separated at least by $\frac{F_s}{M}$ Hz, as otherwise the receiver cannot solve the inherent ambiguity caused by the Doppler displacement, leading to a non-zero error floor even in the noiseless case. This implies that we can support a DFU of up to $F_{DFU} = \frac{F_s}{2M} = \frac{N}{2MT_s}$ Hz, or, equivalently, we require the number of samples per symbol to be at least

$$N = 2Mn_{DFU}.$$

Observe that when there is no DFU, we need to sample the signal, by at least $N = M$ samples per symbol in order to compute $\bar{r}[n]$ for the M possible discrete tones $\frac{n}{M}$, $n = 0, \dots, M-1$. This means that we can guarantee $2F_{DFU}T_s = 1$, and thus by default we support a DFU of $F_{DFU} = \frac{1}{2T_s}$ Hz. For the special MFSK, with $L = 3$ tones per symbol, i.e. $l \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$, every symbol is represented by a frequency pattern consisting of a central tone at $F_C = 0$, and two main tones at $\pm F_m$ Hz. Let $F_m = F_C + m\Delta_{S2S}$ be the main tone for symbols $m = 0, \dots, M-1$, where Δ_{S2S} denotes the separation between two main tones from two adjacent symbols. To support a particular DFU, the sampling frequency must be at least

$$F_s = 2(F_C + \Delta_{S2S}(M-1) + F_{DFU}).$$

To avoid the center tone to be confused with any of the main tones we shall chose $F_C \geq F_{DFU}$. In particular, we chose $F_C = F_{DFU} + \frac{F_s}{N}$. Regarding the separation between main tones, it can be as low as the frequency resolution of our receiver. This is, if we have N samples per symbol, then we can choose $\Delta_{S2S} = n_{S2S} \frac{F_s}{N}$ with $n_{S2S} \in \{1, 2, \dots\}$. Accordingly, we need the number of samples $N = F_s T_s$ to be at least

$$N = 2(n_{S2S}(M-1) + 2n_{DFU} + 1) + 1.$$

For the special MFSK, an important parameter is the modulation index which determines the relative amplitude between the tones of a symbol. Here, we consider the *sqr* waveform with modulation index $\Delta = 60^\circ$. This corresponds to tone coefficients $\alpha_0 = 0.29$ and $\alpha_1 = \alpha_{-1} = 0.35$. First, to observe the impact of the modulation index, we evaluate, via Monte Carlo's method, the mutual information expression in (19). Fig. 1, shows the energy per bit $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ as a function of code rate (R), for the special MFSK modulations with $M = 32$, different modulation indexes and $2n_{DFU} = 300$. As shown in Fig. 1 we have not observed significant performance differences between modulation index $\Delta = 50^\circ$ and $\Delta = 90^\circ$, the later

Fig. 1: Impact of the modulation index for the non-coherent detection over AWGN of a special MFSK modulation with *sqr* waveform, in term of the minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ required for reliable communication versus the code rate R . Modulation order $M = 32$, $2n_{DFU} = 300$ and $n_{S2S} = 1$.

corresponding to no carrier tone. Notice that these results do not show a significant role for the central tone in terms of information rates. However, the presence of the carrier tone can be exploited to separate the Doppler frequency acquisition and tracking from the symbol detection as proposed in [7], [8], reducing the receiver computational complexity at the cost of losing optimally. Notice that, if Doppler frequency acquisition is done only from the carrier tone, then all the energy in the main tones is not exploited for this purpose. Similarly, if symbol detection is done only from the main tones then, all the energy in the carrier tone is not exploited for symbol detection. Only with a joint Doppler and symbol detection, from all the received energy, we can obtain the best performance.

For the discussion on the impact of the DFU, we consider the representative cases of $2n_{DFU} = 1$ and $2n_{DFU} = 300$ in combination with different modulation orders $M \in \{32, 64, 128, 256\}$. Figure 2 depicts the energy per bit $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ as a function of code rate (R), for the classical and special MFSK modulations. In Figure 2 (left), we provide the results for case $2n_{DFU} = 1$, i.e. no Doppler uncertainty, or equivalently, $N = M$ for classical MFSK and $N = 2(M+1)$ for special MFSK, as we can have the minimum possible separation between tones. In Figure 2 (right) we provide the case $2n_{DFU} = 300$. Notice that this implies $N = 300M$ for the MFSK, and $N = 2(M+300)$ for the special MFSK. This, for instance, might correspond to a DFU of 100 Hz and a symbol duration of T_s of 1.5 seconds.

First, we can observe a well known result for non-coherent channels [14], [16], for which, in contrast to coherent channels, the minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ is not obtained as $R \rightarrow 0$, but at a non-trivial rate. In particular, we find the minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ at $R \simeq 0.5$ and $R \simeq 0.8$ for $2n_{DFU} = 1$ and $2n_{DFU} = 300$, respectively. In general, we observe that as we increase n_{DFU} , both the

Fig. 2: Minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ required for reliable communication versus the code rate R for a M -ary FSK modulation of order $M = 32$, with non-coherent detection and AWGN. The figure on the left corresponds to the no DFU case, i.e. $2n_{DFU} = 1$, and the figure on the right corresponds to $2n_{DFU} = 300$.

Fig. 3: Minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ as a function special and classical MFSK with $M=32$.

required $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ and the optimal rate R^* increase. Comparing the performance of the classical and special MFSK modulations, we observe that, at the minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$, for very low Doppler, $2n_{DFU} = 1$, classical outperforms special MFSK, with a gap in terms of minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ of over 2.25 dBs. This is so, both, because all the energy is concentrated in one signaling tone rather than spread over 3 tones, and because the smaller number of samples per symbol. As we increase the DFU to $2n_{DFU} = 300$, and thus the number of samples increases much faster for classical than for special MFSK, the gap reduces to less than 0.5 dBs. Finally, as we observe in Figure 3 this gap remains almost constant as we increase $2n_{DFU}$, suggesting that the spread of energy across tones can never be fully compensated.

B. Receiver Complexity

In terms of receiver computational complexity, specially in situations when large frequency Doppler need to be supported, the main bottleneck of the receiver is at the N -dimensional Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) that is required to compute $r(\frac{n}{N})$ in (7) for $n = 0, \dots, N - 1$, and for every symbol duration T_s . Given that the FFT operation has complexity $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$, we measure the complexity in operations per second as $\frac{N \log N}{T_s}$.

To study the impact of the receiver complexity, we fix the design target DFU to 100Hz, as well as the, received carrier to noise ratio (CNR) level to $CNR = 9.5$ dBHz, and compute the energy per bit to noise power spectral density as $\frac{E_b}{N_0} = CNR - 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{R \log_2 M}{T_s} \right)$ in dBs and the information data rate as $R_D = \frac{R \log_2 M}{T_s}$ in bits per second, where R is the code rate computed from (19), for a range of modulation orders $M \in \{4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024\}$ and a range of possible symbol duration T_s from 0.05 seconds to 3 seconds with a resolution of 0.05 seconds. Figure 4 shows the results of our evaluation. We depict the R_D (top) and the $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ (bottom) as a function of the complexity in operations per second for the classical MFSK (in blue) and special MFSK (in red). We can observe that when limiting the computational complexity, as long as the modulation order and the symbol duration can be freely chosen, the special MFSK clearly outperforms classical MFSK everywhere. This lower receiver computation complexity is thus the main reason for adopting special MFSK instead of classical MFSK modulation in space communications when huge Doppler frequencies of up to 20KHz, need to be supported, [7].

V. DECODER METRICS

In this section, we derive optimal and practical decoder metrics and evaluate them, in terms of both mismatched mutual information, and codeword error rate for the LDPC codes of the TM standard [18] that are typically used for Lunar or

Fig. 4: Information rate in bits per second (top) and $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ in dBs (bottom) as a function of the complexity in operations per second for classical (blue) and special (red) MFSK modulation with DFU = 100 Hz, and CNR = 9.5Hz, and for different modulation orders, and symbols duration.

Lagrangian missions (less than 2 million km distance). From the symbol likelihood information given by the channel transition probability, $p(\mathbf{r}|s)$ in (11), to obtain the soft-information metrics it only remains to map it into reliability information about the associated transmitted bits. Let s^0 denote the true transmitted symbol. For $b = 1, \dots, \log_2 M$ let \mathcal{B}_b^0 denote the set of symbols in $\{0, \dots, M-1\}$ that map into a bit sequence \mathbf{c} of length $\log_2 M$ that has a zero at the b th position. Likewise, let \mathcal{B}_b^1 denote the set of symbols in $\{0, \dots, M-1\}$ that map into a bit sequence \mathbf{c} of length $\log_2 M$ that has a one at the b th position. Then, the decoder metric in terms of log-likelihood (L-value) associated to the b th bit in \mathbf{c} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L(b) &= \log \frac{\mathbb{P}[c(b) = 1|\mathbf{r}]}{\mathbb{P}[c(b) = 0|\mathbf{r}]} = \log \frac{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \mathbb{P}[s^0 = s|\mathbf{r}]}{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \mathbb{P}[s^0 = s|\mathbf{r}]} \\ &= \log \frac{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} p(\mathbf{r}|s^0 = s)}{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} p(\mathbf{r}|s^0 = s)} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

$$= \log \frac{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \Psi_s(\mathbf{r})}{\sum_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \Psi_s(\mathbf{r})} \quad (21)$$

where (20) follows from the Bayes rule after assuming independent and uniformly distributed bits within a codeword.

The optimal ML decoder metric is obtained by substituting into (21), $\Psi_s(\mathbf{r})$ in (12) for general tone patterns, or (15) and (14), for classical and special MFSK, respectively.

The optimal ML decoder metric is computationally complex and numerically unstable, mainly, due to the evaluation of the modified Bessel function and the summations over the Doppler frequencies tone candidates. To alleviate both these effects, next we provide approximate expressions for the decoder metric and thus for the associated transition probability $p^*(\mathbf{r}^*|m^0 = m)$. In that case, the mutual information associated to a non-optimal decoder metric $I^*(S; R^*)$ is given by the ‘‘mismatched’’ mutual information [19], [20], which in this case can be computed from (19) by replacing $\Delta_{s,s^0}(\mathbf{r})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{s,s^0}^*(\mathbf{r}) &= \frac{p^*(\mathbf{r}|s)}{p^*(\mathbf{r}|s^0)} \\ &= \frac{\Psi_s^*(\mathbf{r})}{\Psi_{s^0}^*(\mathbf{r})}. \end{aligned}$$

First, to avoid the complexity of the double summations, over symbols in (21) and over Doppler frequencies in (12), the log likelihood ratio may be approximated as

$$L^{DM}(b) = \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \log(\Psi_s^{DM}(\mathbf{r})) - \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \log(\Psi_s^{DM}(\mathbf{r}))$$

which, since $\sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \frac{\lambda_{l,s}}{2} = \frac{\lambda}{2}$ for all symbols, we have

$$\log(\Psi_s^{DM}(\mathbf{r})) = \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \log I_0 \left(\sqrt{\lambda_{l,s} \bar{r}(m_{j,s} + k_D)} \right) \quad (22)$$

which we refer to as the *dual-max* decoder metric. Alternatively, since the modified Bessel function $I_0(x)$ with $x > 0$ increases exponentially with x , it is numerically more stable to compute instead $I'_0(x) = e^{-x} I_0(x)$. In terms of $I'_0(x)$, now we can rewrite (22) as

$$\log(\Psi_s^{DM}(\mathbf{r})) = \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \sqrt{\lambda_{l,s} \bar{r}(m_{j,s} + k_D)} + \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \log I'_0 \left(\sqrt{\lambda_{l,s} \bar{r}(m_{j,s} + k_D)} \right) \right).$$

Note that the logarithm and the Bessel functions always appear together and so this combined function can be implemented as a single table lookup. A piecewise linear approximation for this nonlinear function is given in [15] and references therein.

Next, if we only consider the exponential approximation of the Bessel function, i.e. $I'_0(x) \approx e^{-x}$, we have

$$L^{EDM}(b) = \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \log(\Psi_s^{EDM}(\mathbf{r})) - \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \log(\Psi_s^{EDM}(\mathbf{r}))$$

with

$$\log(\Psi_s^{EDM}(\mathbf{r})) = \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \sqrt{\lambda_{l,s} \bar{r}(m_{j,s} + k_D)}$$

which we refer to as the *exponential dual-max* decoder metric.

The next approximation we propose is closely related to the *square law combining* metric proposed in [14], which consists in simply scaling \mathbf{r} (i.e. the square output of the matched filter). Its extension to the general orthogonal signaling considered here and to the Doppler uncertainty case which we refer to as *energy max* metric, reads

$$L^{EM}(b) = \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \log(\Psi_s^{EM}(\mathbf{r})) - \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \log(\Psi_s^{EM}(\mathbf{r})) \quad (23)$$

with

$$\log(\Psi_s^{EM}(\mathbf{r})) = \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \alpha \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} r(m_{j,s} + k_D).$$

where α is the scaling factor that maximizes the mismatched mutual information using $\Delta_m^*(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\Psi_s^{EM^*}(\mathbf{r})}{\Psi_s^{EM}(\mathbf{r})}$, and is thus a function of $\frac{E_s}{N_0}$, as well as all the system parameters, i.e. N and M . This function can be pre-computed and stored in a look-up table. However, this might be something that we want to avoid, for instance, if the system needs to work for arbitrary symbol durations, i.e. N .

Notice that for all the above approximations, while the computation of the mismatched mutual information only depends on $\frac{E_s}{N_0}$ through λ , the evaluation of the decoder metrics depends on both the estimation of $\frac{E_s}{N_0}$ and the noise power σ^2 separately, since $\bar{r}[n] = \frac{2}{\sigma^2} r[n]$. In practice, it might be useful to obtain parameter free transition probabilities that do not depend on the estimation of the signal and noise powers. For that, in [16] a parameter free transition probability approximation was proposed for the non-Doppler uncertainty case, which can be simply extended to the Doppler uncertainty situation by letting

$$p^{\text{EMF}}(\mathbf{r}|s) = \frac{\max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} r(m_{j,s} + k_D)}{\sum_{s=0}^{M-1} \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} r(m_{j,s} + k_D)}.$$

Then

$$L^{\text{EMF}}(b) = \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \log(\Psi_s^{\text{EMF}}(\mathbf{r})) - \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \log(\Psi_s^{\text{EMF}}(\mathbf{r})). \quad (24)$$

with

$$\log(\Psi_s^{\text{EMF}}(\mathbf{r})) = \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} r(m_{j,s} + k_D)$$

Notice that (24) does not depend on the scaling factors λ and $\frac{2}{\sigma^2}$, which themselves depend on the signal and noise power. We refer to this approximation as the *energy max free ratio* approximation.

Finally, we also propose an heuristic extension of the energy max free ratio, by considering instead powers of the sum of received energy, i.e. $\left(\sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \bar{r}(m_{j,s} + k_D) \right)^p$. We refer to the associated decoder metric as the *energy-p max free* metric, whose L-values are computed as

$$L^{\text{EMF-p}}(b) = \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^0} \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \log(\Psi_s^{\text{EMF-p}}(\mathbf{r})) - \max_{s \in \mathcal{B}_b^1} \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} \log(\Psi_s^{\text{EMF-p}}(\mathbf{r}))$$

with

$$\log(\Psi_s^{\text{EMF-p}}(\mathbf{r})) = \max_{k_D \in \mathcal{K}_D} p \log \left(\sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \bar{r}(m_{j,s} + k_D) \right).$$

A. Mismatched Mutual Information Evaluation

In Figures 5 and 6, we compare the different decoder metrics proposed for the classical and special MFSK modulations, respectively. The figures on the left show the case of no Doppler uncertainty, $N = M$ and on the right the case $N = 300M$. Figures show the required $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ for reliable communication as a function of the code rate for the different decoder metrics discussed above. Solid lines provide the curves for the parameter dependent approximations whereas dashed lines correspond to parameter free metrics. In general, we can observe a very good performance for all the parameter dependent approximation, including the simpler energy max approximation (solid green) with only minimal losses as compared with the optimal ML performance. Regarding the parameter free approximations (dashed curves), we observe that it is possible to obtain a fairly good performance by properly adjusting the power p applied

Fig. 5: Minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ required for reliable communication versus the code rate R for a M-ary FSK modulation of order $M = 32$, with non-coherent detection in AWGN, for $2 \cdot DFU \cdot T_s = 1$ (left) and $2 \cdot DFU \cdot T_s = 300$ (right). Comparison between different transition probability approximations.

Fig. 6: Minimum $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ required for reliable communication versus the code rate R for a M-ary FSK modulation of order $M = 32$, with non-coherent detection in AWGN, for $2 \cdot DFU \cdot T_s = 1$ (left) and $2 \cdot DFU \cdot T_s = 300$ (right). Comparison between different transition probability approximations.

to the *energy-p max free* approximation. Notice that, either for classical or special MFSK, for $N = M$ choosing $p = 2$ and for $N = 300M$ choosing $p = 8$ provides a fairly good performance for a large range of coding rates, which indicates it is feasible to use the energy-p max free approximation in practice together with several well design FEC available codes.

B. LDPC Performance Evaluation

Finally, in Figure 7 we show the codeword error rate (CWER) as a function of $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$. We considered the TM LDPC codes specified in [18] with information word size 1024 bits and code rates $1/2$, $2/3$, and $4/5$. For the LDPC decoder we used the layered belief propagation decoding algorithm with normalized min-sum approximation, scaling factor 0.75 and 50 iterations. We compare the optimal ML metric, together with the suboptimal dual-max and energy-8 max free metrics (in the left for the classical and on the right for the special MFSK). As a reference, we also show the minimum energy-per-bit

obtained evaluating the mutual information for the optimal rate (green) and for the different code rates considered (dashed lines). First, observe that for classical MFSK, the optimal code rate is at 0.74, and thus, the closest code rate $4/5 = 0.8$ that we evaluate obtains the best performance. We also observe that both suboptimal decoder metrics either parameter dependent or free parameter provide very close to optimal performance for all code rates. Similar conclusions can be drawn for the special MFSK. In this case the minimum energy per bit is achieved at 0.76, which is almost identical for the evaluated code rates $2/3$ and $4/5$. In this case, the performance loss incurred by the suboptimal decoders is larger than for the classical MFSK, but still close to the ML curves.

VI. CONCLUSION

We studied the impact of the Doppler frequency uncertainty on the mutual information of non-coherent channels. For that, we considered a general form of orthogonal MFSK modulation, where symbols are represented by a tone pattern.

Fig. 7: Simulated CWER results as a function of the $\frac{E_b}{N_0}$ for the different TM LDPC code rates. For classical (left) with $M = 32$, $2n_{DFU} = 300$, and $N = 2n_{DFU}M = 9600$, $F_s = 3200$ Hz. For special (right), $M = 128$, $2n_{DFU} = 300$, $F_C = n_C \frac{F_s}{N}$ with $n_C = n_{DFU} + 1$, $n_{S2S} = 1$, $N = 2(n_C + n_{S2S}(M - 1) + n_{DFU}) + 1 = 857$ and $F_s = 571.33$ Hz.

The formulation is general enough to include important orthogonal modulations like the classical and the special MFSK modulations. We showed that in terms of information data rates or required energy per bits, classical MFSK always outperforms special MFSK under no computation complexity constraints at the receiver, thanks to concentrating all the transmitted energy in a single tone. In contrast, for a fixed computation complexity, we showed that the special MFSK always outperforms the classical MFSK thanks to a dramatically decrease in the computational complexity (not scaling with the modulation order) at the cost of a small reduction in the mutual information which comes from spreading of signal energy across multiple tones. In addition, we showed that the code rate that minimizes the required energy-per-bit to noise power spectral ratio for reliable communications, increases with the product between the DFU and the symbol duration or, equivalently, the minimum number of required samples per

symbol. We provided the mismatched mutual information for different suboptimal, but practical decoding metrics, including parameter free metrics that do not require the estimation of the signal and noise power, and evaluated the performance of the LDPC codes used for telemetry in deep space missions. The numerical results showed near-optimal performance for the parameter dependent approximated metrics as well as for the parameter free metrics as the samples per symbols are increased. There are several possible extensions for this work including considered the Doppler rate effect, fading channels, and low-complexity detectors. The mutual expression derived can also be used for code optimization when considering orthogonal signal sets with non-coherent detection, in line with the works conducted in [16] for bit interleaved coded modulations or in [21], [22] for Turbo decoding.

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